

Time and Temperature Dependence of Static, Creep, and Fatigue Behavior for CF/Epoxy Strands

Masayuki Nakada¹, Yasushi Miyano¹, Ryosuke Nakamae¹, and Rokuro Muki²

¹ Materials System Research Laboratory, Kanazawa Institute of Technology,
Yatsukaho, Matto, Ishikawa 924-0838, Japan

² Civil & Environmental Engineering Department, University of California at Los Angeles,
Los Angeles, CA 90095-1593, U.S.A.

SUMMARY: A prediction method of fatigue strength under an arbitrary frequency, temperature, and stress ratio for polymer composites was proposed by measuring the constant-strain-rate (CSR) strength at various strain-rates and temperatures and the fatigue strength at a single frequency and various temperatures. This method is based upon the four hypotheses: (A) same failure process under constant strain-rate (CSR), creep, and fatigue loadings, (B) same time-temperature superposition principle for all failure strengths, (C) linear cumulative damage law for monotonic loading, and (D) linear dependence of fatigue strength upon stress ratio. Tensile CSR, creep, and fatigue tests of epoxy resin impregnated carbon fiber strands as used for unidirectional CFRP at various loading rates, frequencies, and temperatures were performed. Experimental verification of the prediction method is discussed for the tensile fatigue strength of this strand by using these results.

KEY WORDS: Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics, Fatigue, Life Prediction, Time-Temperature Dependent Properties

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behavior of polymer resins exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass-transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Thus, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of FRP using polymer resins as matrices also depends on time and temperature even below T_g which is within the normal operating-temperature range. These examples are shown by Aboudi et al. [1], Sullivan [12], Gates [3], Miyano et al. [6,11].

The time-temperature dependence of the flexural CSR (constant strain-rate), creep, and fatigue strengths of various CFRP laminates has been studied by Miyano et al. [2,5,7]. It was observed that the fracture modes are almost identical under the three types of loading over a wide range of time and temperature. Similar results were also reported by Karayaka et al. [4] at room temperature. The literature survey indicates the validity of the two hypotheses for CFRP: the same failure process and the same time-temperature superposition principle for CSR, creep, and fatigue failure.

In our previous papers [8-10], a prediction method for fatigue strength of CFRP under an arbitrary frequency, stress ratio, and temperature was proposed based on the above two hypotheses and two additional hypotheses: the linear cumulative damage law for monotonic loading and the linear dependence of fatigue strength upon stress ratio. The validity of the method and the hypotheses was confirmed by three-point bending tests of satin-woven CFRP laminates and others.

In this paper, this prediction method is applied to the tensile fatigue strength of unidirectional CFRP and its validity is confirmed experimentally by using the results of tests for epoxy resin impregnated strand considered to be unidirectional CFRP.

PREDICTION PROCEDURE OF FATIGUE STRENGTH

The prediction method rests on the four hypotheses, (A) same failure process under CSR, creep, and fatigue loadings, (B) same time-temperature superposition principle for all failure

- T, T₀ : temperature, reference temperature
- f, f' : frequency, reduced frequency
- t_s, t_c, t_f : time to failure under constant-strain rate(CSR), creep and fatigue loading
- t_s' ; t_c' ; t_f' : reduced time to failure
- a_{T0}(T) : time-temperature shift factor (a_{T0}(T) = t_s/t_s' = t_c/t_c' = t_f/t_f' = f' / f)
- R : stress ratio (R = σ_{min}/σ_{max})
- N_f : number of cycles to failure (N_f = f t_f)
- σ_s, σ_c, σ_f : CSR, creep, and fatigue strength
- σ_{f;0}, σ_{f;1} : σ_f for R=0 and R=1

Fig.1 Prediction procedure of fatigue strength of CFRP composites

strengths, (C) linear cumulative damage law for nondecreasing stress process, and (D) linear dependence of fatigue strength upon stress ratio.

When these hypotheses are met, the fatigue strength under an arbitrary combination of frequency, stress ratio, and temperature can be determined based on the following test results: (a) master curve of CSR strength and (b) master curve of fatigue strength for zero stress ratio. The master curve of CSR strength can be constructed from the test results at various constant strain-rates and temperatures. On the other hand, the master curve of fatigue strength at zero stress ratio can be constructed from the test results at a single frequency under various temperatures. We consider the CSR strength is the fatigue strength at $R=0$ and the number of cycles to failure $N_f=1/2$ based on the similarity of the two loading histories.

The outline of this method is shown schematically in Fig.1 together with definitions of some notations. The detail of the method will be presented with experimental results.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of Specimen

The unidirectional CFRP (epoxy resin impregnated carbon fiber strand; CF/Ep strand) produced by filament winding method consists of high strength carbon fibers TORAYCA T400-3K (TORAY) and a general purpose epoxy resin EPIKOTE 828 (YUKA SHELL EPOXY). The CF/Ep strand was cured at 70°C for 12 hours and postcured at 150°C for 4 hours, and then at 190°C for 2 hours. The glass-transition temperature T_g of the epoxy resin is 112°C. The diameter of CF/Ep strand is approximately 1 mm.

Test Procedures

The tensile test specimens of CF/Ep strand were prepared as shown in Fig.2. The tensile CSR tests were conducted at 6 temperatures between 50 and 150°C, by using an Instron type testing machine with small temperature controlled chamber as shown in Fig.3. Loading rates (cross-head speeds) were 0.01, 1, and 100mm/min. The creep tests were conducted at 3 temperatures by using creep testing machines. The fatigue tests were conducted under several constant temperatures at 2 loading frequencies $f=2$ and 0.02Hz by using an electro-hydraulic servo testing machine with small temperature controlled chamber as shown in Fig.3. Stress ratio R (minimum stress/maximum stress) was 0.1. Additional fatigue tests were conducted under several constant temperatures at $f=2$ Hz and $R=0.5$. The tensile CSR, creep, and fatigue strengths are calculated by using the cross-sectional area of carbon fiber strand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Master Curve of CSR Strength

The left side of Fig.4 shows the tensile CSR strength σ_s versus time to failure t_s at various temperatures T , where t_s is the time period from initial loading to maximum load in constant strain-rate tests. The master curve was constructed by shifting σ_s at constant temperatures other than reference temperature T_0 along the log scale of t_s so that they overlap on σ_s at the reference temperature or on each other to form a single smooth curve as shown in the right side of Fig.4. Since σ_s at various temperatures can be superimposed smoothly, the time-temperature superposition principle is applicable for σ_s . The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ is defined by

$$a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{t_s}{t'_s} \quad (1)$$

Fig.2 Configuration of CF/Ep strand Specimen

Fig.3 Configuration of the tensile tests for strand

Fig.4 Master curve of the tensile CSR strength for CF/Ep strand

where, t'_s is reduced time to failure. The shift factors for the tensile CSR strength of CF/Ep strand obtained experimentally in Fig.4 are plotted in solid circles and connected by solid line in Fig.5. Also, plotted by open circles in Fig.5 is the shift factor for the creep compliance of matrix resin; these plots agree well with those for tensile CSR strength. It can be presumed from this agreement and the role of load transmission to fibers on matrix resin that the time and temperature dependence of the tensile CSR strength of CF/Ep strand is controlled by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin. Both of these shift factors are quantitatively in good agreement with two Arrhenius' equations with different activation energies ΔH :

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K.mol)].

Master Curve of Creep Strength

A prediction method of creep strength σ_c from the master curve of CSR strength using the linear cumulative damage law was presented in our previous paper [8]. Let $t_s(\sigma)$ and $t_c(\sigma)$ be the CSR and creep failure time for the stress σ . Suppose that the material experiences a nondecreasing stress history $\sigma(t)$ for $0 - t - t^*$ where t^* is the failure time under this stress history. The linear cumulative damage law states

$$\int_0^{t^*} \frac{dt}{t_c[\sigma(t)]} = 1 \quad (3)$$

When $\sigma(t)$ is equal to constant stress σ_0 , the above formula reduces to $t^* = t_c(\sigma_0)$.

Fig.5 Time - temperature shift factors for the tensile CSR strength

The left side of upper graph in Fig.6 shows the creep strength σ_c at three different temperatures which are shifted using the shift factor for CSR strength to the data at the reference temperature $T_0 = 50^\circ\text{C}$ on the right side. In the right side, the solid curve represents the master curve of creep strength calculated based on equation (3) using the master curve of CSR strength plotted in dashed curve. The agreement between the predicted curve and the creep test results is satisfactory except that for $T = 50^\circ\text{C}$. It can be presumed that this disagreement is caused by the physical aging of matrix resin. The same testing were carried out for CF/Ep strand exposed at the aging condition of 110°C and 6×10^4 min. The agreement for all testing temperature shown in the lower graph in Fig.6 indicates the validity of the linear cumulative damage law and a common shift factor.

Master Curve of Fatigue Strength

We regard the fatigue strength σ_f either as a function of the number of cycles to failure N_f or of the time to failure $t_f=N_f/f$ for a combination of frequency f , stress ratio R , temperature T and denote them by $\sigma_f(N_f; f, R, T)$ or $\sigma_f(t_f; f, R, T)$. Further, we consider the CSR strength $\sigma_s(t_f; T)$ the fatigue strength at $N_f=1/2$, $R=0$, and $t_f=1/(2f)$; this is motivated by closeness of the line connecting the origin and $(\pi, 1)$ and the curve $[1+\sin(t-\pi/2)]/2$ for $0 < t < \pi$. At this point, we introduce special symbols for fatigue strength at zero and unit stress ratios by $\sigma_{f,0}$ and $\sigma_{f,1}$ where the latter corresponds to creep strength.

Fig.6 Master curve for tensile creep strength of CF/Ep strand

To describe the master curve of $\sigma_{f,0}$, we need the reduced frequency f' in addition to the reduced time t_f' , each defined by

$$f' = f \cdot a_{T_0}(T), \quad t_f' = \frac{t_f}{a_{T_0}(T)} = \frac{N_f}{f'} \quad (4)$$

We introduce two alternative expressions for the master curve at zero stress ratio: $\sigma_{f,0}(t_f'; f', T_0)$ and $\sigma_{f,0}(t_f'; N_f, T_0)$. In the latter expression, the explicit reference to frequency is suppressed in favor of N_f . Note that the master curve of fatigue strength at $N_f=1/2$ is regarded as the master curve of CSR strength. Equation (4) enables one to construct the master curve

from the tests at a single frequency under various temperatures.

Figure 7 displays, for three temperatures, the fatigue strength $\sigma_{f:0}$ versus the number of cycles to failure N_f ($\sigma_{f:0}$ - N_f curve) at a frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$, stress ratio $R=0.1$ together with the CSR strength which is regarded as the fatigue strength at $N_f=1/2$, $R=0$. In the analysis to follow, we regard $\sigma_{f:0}$ to be the master curves at $R=0.1$. In the upper side of Fig.8, master curves of $\sigma_{f:0}$ versus the reduced time to failure for three frequencies at the reference temperature $T_0=50^\circ\text{C}$ are depicted in solid curves using the shift factor for CSR strength; the master curve for CSR strength is included in the figure in dashed curve. The master curves of $\sigma_{f:0}$ - t_f' for fixed N_f are constructed by connecting the points of the same N_f on the curves of each frequency as shown in the lower side of Fig.8.

The predicted $\sigma_{f:0}$ - N_f curves at $f=0.02\text{Hz}$ under two temperature levels are displayed in Fig.9 together with test data. These curves are constructed from the master curves in the lower side of Fig.8 by use of (4). Since the predicted $\sigma_{f:0}$ - N_f curves capture test data satisfactorily, the time-temperature superposition principle for the CSR strength also holds for the fatigue strength indicating the validity of the hypothesis (B) for fatigue strength.

Fig.7 Tensile fatigue strength versus number of cycles to failure CF/Ep strand

Fig.8 Master curves for tensile fatigue strength of CF/Ep strand

Fig.9 Prediction of the tensile fatigue strength by using the master curves of the tensile fatigue strength

Prediction of Fatigue Strength for Arbitrary Stress Ratio

We have the master curve for creep strength $\sigma_c(t_c'; T_0)$ from which follows the creep strength

at any temperature T . The creep strength, in turn, may be regarded as the fatigue strength $\sigma_{f,1}(t_f; f, T)$ at unit stress ratio $R=1$ and arbitrary frequency f with $t_c=t_f$. Further, from the master curve for fatigue strength at zero stress ratio $\sigma_{f,0}(t_f', f', T_0)$ obtainable from tests with a single frequency and various temperatures as shown in Fig.8, we can deduce by use of equation (5) the fatigue strength $\sigma_{f,0}(t_f; f, T)$ at zero stress ratio for any frequency f and temperature T . Implementing hypothesis (D), we propose a formula to estimate the fatigue strength $\sigma_f(t_f; f, R, T)$ at an arbitrary combination of f, R, T by

$$\sigma_f(t_f; f, R, T) = \sigma_{f,1}(t_f; f, T)R + \sigma_{f,0}(t_f; f, T)(1 - R) \quad (5)$$

Figure 10 displays the experimental data of σ_f-t_f at $f=2\text{Hz}$, $R=0.5$, and $T=50, 110, 150^\circ\text{C}$. The curves of $R=0$ and $R=1$ represent the least squares fit for experimental data of fatigue test at $R=0.1$ and creep test. The curve of $R=0.5$ is calculated from equation (5) on the basis of the curves for $\sigma_{f,0}$ and $\sigma_{f,1}$. As can be seen, the predictions correspond with the test data adequately.

CONCLUSION

Tensile CSR, creep, and fatigue tests for unidirectional CFRP were carried out under various temperatures and loading rates. We observed remarkable dependence of these strengths upon temperature, loading rate as well as the number of cycles to failure. The fatigue prediction method proposed previously for flexural fatigue strength of satin-woven CFRP laminate [8] is applied successfully to the tensile fatigue strength of unidirectional CFRP.

Fig.10 Prediction of tensile fatigue strength under stress ratio $R=0.5$

REFERENCES

1. Aboudi, J. and G. Cederbaum, "Analysis of Viscoelastic Laminated Composite Plates", *Composite Structures*, 12 (1989), 243-256.
2. Enyama, J., M.K. McMurray, M. Nakada and Y. Miyano, "Effects of Stress Ratio on Flexural Fatigue Behavior of a Satin Woven CFRP Laminate", *Proceedings of 3rd Japan SAMPE*, Vol. 2: (1993), 2418-2421.
3. Gates, T., "Experimental Characterization of Nonlinear Rate Dependent Behavior in Advanced Polymer Matrix Composites", *Experimental Mechanics*, (1992), 68-73.
4. Karakaya, M. and P. Kurath, "Deformation and Fatigue Behavior of Woven Composites Laminates", *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, 116 (1994), 222-232.
5. McMurray, M.K., J. Enyama, M. Nakada and Y. Miyano, "Loading Rate and Temperature Dependence on Flexural Fatigue Behavior of a Satin Woven CFRP Laminate", *Proceedings of 38th SAMPE*, No. 2 (1993), 1944-1956.
6. Miyano, Y., M. Kanemitsu, T. Kunio and H. Kuhn, "Role of Matrix Resin on Fracture Strengths of Unidirectional CFRP", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 20 (1986), 520-538.
7. Miyano, Y., M.K. McMurray, J. Enyama and M. Nakada, "Loading Rate and Temperature Dependence on Flexural Fatigue Behavior of a Satin Woven CFRP laminate", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 28 (1994), 1250-1260.
8. Miyano, Y., M. Nakada, M.K. McMurray and R. Muki, "Prediction of Flexural Fatigue Strength of CFRP Composites under Arbitrary Frequency, Stress Ratio and Temperature", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 31 (1997), 619-638.
9. Miyano, Y., M. Nakada and R. Muki, "Prediction of Fatigue Life of a Conical Shaped Joint System for Fiber Reinforced Plastics under Arbitrary Frequency, Load Ratio and Temperature", *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Materials*, 1 (1997), 143-159.
10. Nakada, M., T. Ishiguro and Y. Miyano, "Prediction of Flexural Fatigue Life for Unidirectional CFRP Laminates", *Proceedings of International Conference on Composite Materials 11*, Vol. 2 (1997), 167-176.
11. Nakada, M., M.K. McMurray, N. Kitade, M. Mohri and Y. Miyano, "Role of Matrix Resin on the Flexural Fatigue Behavior of Unidirectional Pitch Based Carbon Fiber Laminates", *Proceedings of International Conference on Composite Materials 9*, Vol. 4 (1993), 731-738.
12. Sullivan, J., "Creep and Physical Aging of Composites", *Composite Science and Technology*, 39 (1990), 207-232.